

Implementation of Social Learning to Increase Community Participation in Protected Forest Management on Raja Island Monano District North Gorontalo Regency

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Abstract:- This study aims to explore the extent to which the value of social learning is implemented in people's lives especially the community managing protected forests in the village of Dunu. The reason for choosing the Dunu village community is due to the characteristics of the people who live around protected forests and have a livelihood as gardeners and fishermen. Social learning really needs to be implemented in the Dunu village community in order to preserve the forest which until now the Raja Island forest is a forest that still has 100% sustainability in the province of Gorontalo. The data analysis technique uses the Miles and Huberman interactive model which is carried out in the form of three components namely data reduction data presentation and verification/drawing conclusions. The results of the study indicate that the application of Social Learning can increase community participation in managing and conserving forests. If the concepts and values of Social Learning can be implemented properly community participation can be increased. Increased community participation can have an impact on the realization of forest management and conservation which is a component of life. Empirical evidence in this study shows that social learning has a very good role in community participation especially in the preservation and management of the Raja forest which is located in the village of Dunu Monano District North Gorontalo Regency. The cause is social learning which is reflected in terms of building communication between forest institutions village government and fellow community groups showing a good role in increasing welfare and the level of community participation.

Keywords:- Social Learning, Society participation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Forests have ecological functions namely as a feeding ground spawning ground and nursery ground for various types of animals. Economic function the forest is a place to meet the needs of the community either in the form of the use of firewood charcoal and medicines. By the Indonesian government forests are highly conserved by involving the participation of the community to make good use of and preserve them. However several realities in the field show that several areas are experiencing threats and disturbances

both in the form of encroachment and illegal cultivation which continue to increase from time to time.

Community involvement in forest management should be a priority for the government to maintain its sustainability. The forest congress held in Jakarta in 1978 with the theme "forest for people" stated that the condition of forests in 1978 was still relatively good but different from current conditions. This unfavorable condition is characterized by illegal logging and the expansion of cultivation/agricultural areas which have resulted in many floods and landslides in recent years.

Several previous studies that examined the same thing were research conducted by Muro & Jeffry (2012), said that community participation plays an ongoing role as a center for natural resource management even though little knowledge about good processes or results. The success of the participatory process encourages researchers and practitioners to research and develop new approaches methods and models of community engagement.

Another study was conducted by Berkes (2009) that the strategies that must be taken to facilitate or improve collaboration management include bridging and producing collaborative knowledge (bridging and co-producing knowledge); participatory research; monitoring in collaboration (collaborate monitoring); building participation scenarios (participatory scenario building); measures the even distribution of collaboration management power and accountability.

Social learning theory assumes that people learn social behavior by observing and imitating the models they do by watching other people. Community participation in forest management can be carried out first by certain people such as forestry officials village officials community leaders and some local communities who can then set an example and be emulated by other communities. The important role of government (forest institutions) and community leaders is urgently needed in seeking community involvement in forest management and preservation.

North Gorontalo Regency has one of the forests that is still preserved. The forest on Raja Island is a protected forest located in Dunu Village Monano District. The livelihoods of the people living around the forest are gardening and fishing. Most of the people use natural

resources around the forest to support their daily needs. Providing understanding to the surrounding community in managing forests can be done by providing examples by forest rangers village officials and community leaders which is the initial action that can be taken as a process of outreach to the community. Involving local communities in proper forest management is the duty of forest institutions to keep forests in good condition. Based on this the application of social learning is expected to be the right solution for involving community participation in managing forests properly as a source of life now and in the future.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

Community participation is community involvement from the approach to the actual community participation approach (Arnstein 1969). Community participation is a form of direct involvement in which the community either individually or even through an organizational group can exchange information express opinions and interests and has the potential to influence a decision or result specifically (Beckley et al. 2005).

A participatory definition both descriptive and normative must especially emphasize that all community development and development are processes that can only be successful if carried out together with and by the people themselves especially the poor (Muller 2006). Communities must actively participate in determining and carrying out government assistance program efforts and thus can determine their own living conditions from the moment of decision making implementation supervision to maintenance of a program. Community participation has two dimensions (Daniel and Nieldalina 2006) including direct participation and (2) indirect participation. Direct participation includes the involvement of stakeholders in activities such as attending meetings on forest protection taking an active part in meetings labor contributions to forest management monitoring and patrols for forest protection. Indirect participation refers to individual obedience to comply with forestry regulations and protection motivate other people and family members to participate in forest protection efforts provide moral support to the community to ensure fairness and transparency in forest management.

Social identity factors as self-categorization psychology organization and sources of motivation will directly affect community participation in an organization (Himadri, 2000). Cohen (1997) divides community participation into four stages, namely: (1) the program planning stage which is realized through participation in meetings for decision making (2) the implementation stage which is an important stage in development because the core of development is the implementation of a real form of participation. This stage of participation is classified into three stages namely participation in the form of contribution of ideas the form of material contributions and forms of action as a member of the program (3) the stage of enjoying the results which can be used as indicators of the success of community participation at the planning and

implementation stages of the program. Seeing the position of the community as the subject of development the greater the perceived benefits of the program meaning that the program is successful and on target and (4) the evaluation and monitoring stage is an important stage because community participation in this stage is feedback that can provide input for improvement for the implementation of the next program. Huraerah (2008) explains that the success of community participation is influenced by the initiator of participation either from the government or non-governmental organizations (NGOs).

According to social learning theory behavior personality and environment are three factors that influence individual attitudes. It is said in the theory that social factors or environmental cognitive and behavioral factors are important factors in learning. According to Kusumanto et al. (2005) that the dimensions of social learning consist of (1) a collection of knowledge development among group members (2) the existence of knowledge and information sharing among different stakeholders (3) building communication and relationships among stakeholders and (4) strategic capacity building.

Social learning as explained is a very important social learning process in forest management and must be supported by a good understanding and level of community education. Social learning in this study is a process where there is an opportunity to exchange ideas exchange information and knowledge and it is hoped that there will be good cooperation between the community and the managers and stakeholders. As a result it is hoped that forest management will be good if there is a good community social learning process.

Interestingly the phenomenon that exists in Gorontalo is that the Village Head as the traditional leader is actually elected through an electoral system like the election of heads of state. In order to produce quality leaders the value of Moelolo's local wisdom is also an indicator. This is as previously stated by Chigudu (2015) that the value of local wisdom is an asset in reducing the possibility of fraud in elections. This model behavior is inherent in the leader who in the Gorontalo language is called Olongia or a prominent person or leader who is chosen based on his character and example (Haluty 2014). Olongia in its implementation has several functions namely; head of government chair of the council and chair of security/defence. This implies that the olongia controls the two pillars of government namely the executive and the legislature.

Research on social learning on community welfare by Hemerijck (2005). The results of his research show that most member states of the European Union (EU) have carried out comprehensive welfare reforms since the 1990s. In addition it is said that in social life active participation (in work) is very important because participation in social life is crucial to get respect from others. Mutual respect is an opportunity to actively participate in society that must be done by everyone.

Yamauchi (2005) conducted a study that aims to examine the effect of a generation's social learning on household income in the village. Next it also examines the effect of cross-community schooling on household income. His research shows that educated households are able to earn higher incomes than uneducated households. Yamauchi estimates the marginal effect of learning on harvest income from each field. It turns out that learning in the social learning process has an effect on increasing household income. As previously explained research that says community welfare affects community participation is carried out by Rahut et al. (2015) and Akamani & Hall (2014).

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In this research the researcher looks at the problem under study and depends on the desired approach. Therefore in carrying out this research phenomenological research is used namely the researcher has a broad view and tries to understand the meaning of events and their relationships to objects in certain situations. In this research the researcher looks at the problem under study and depends on the desired approach. Therefore in carrying out this research phenomenological research is used namely the researcher has a broad view and tries to understand the meaning of events and their relationships to objects in certain situations. The type of research used is qualitative research. Qualitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of postpositivism used to research on natural object conditions (as opposed to experiments) where the researcher is the key instrument data collection techniques are carried out by triangulation (combined) data analysis is inductive/qualitative and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization (Sugiyono, 2018).

IV. DISCUSSION

A. *Sharing Information and Knowledge*

The threat of forest destruction is increasing day by day most of the forest damage is due to the opening of new land that does not follow ecological or environmental principles. Lots of forests are destroyed only for certain interests of individuals or groups or institutions without any consideration for their preservation. The development of residential areas or expansion areas that require new land for regional development will result in the clearing of forests. As a result of all of this will damage the balance of the environmental ecosystem forests that have been damaged a lot will have a bad influence on the environment.

With the understanding of the environment above efforts to preserve the environment are efforts to preserve environmental components and their inherent functions and interactions that occur between these components. There are differences in function between components and utilization in development conservation is not understood as restricted use. However preservation should be understood as utilization that pays attention to the function of each component and the interaction between

environmental components and in the end it is hoped that environmental preservation will guarantee the existence of each environmental component.

Preservation of the function of an environment using environmental communication has been carried out in the research of Chandrabuwono and Atika (2019) which is located in the Sungai Tabuk community. The results of this study explain the changes in the Tabuk River community due to the appropriate environmental communication approach. This can be used as a reference in the case of creating sustainable forests for forest village communities so that the two main functions of sustainable forests can occur. The same process in carrying out successful environmental communication is by optimizing community participation.

Through the process of social learning the community will become more competent to various problems in their community environment as well as in a more macro environment (Siswanto et al. 2014). The competence of community members can be demonstrated by two components namely social responsibility and capacity. Being responsible for always trying to improve living conditions for a better and more prosperous must be done both personally and in life together in a team or community group through the process of social learning. The social learning process by building communication with stakeholders (NGOs managers local/central government academics/practitioners and the community) will be able to increase competence and productivity and community welfare if the factors supporting the success of social learning can be fulfilled properly (Siswanto et al. 2014).

This is as conveyed by Mr. Bura as the forest supervisor of Raja Island on 12 May 2022 that Information about: "the importance of forest conservation owned by the community around Raja Island was obtained from the socialization carried out by the father (village head) which was delivered at every village community activity such as weddings death commemorations and several other village activities such as activities carried out by RemaMuda and Karang Taruna. Socialization using the most effective events organized by the community so that the community can make knowledge about forest conservation a very important and routine thing".

The role of community participation in forest management is very important. The consideration is that the people living around the forest are a threat and a nuisance to a forest area. This is because the community tries to meet the needs of life from forest resource products. By involving the community in forest management it is part of the solution to prevent various disturbances and threats in the forestry sector (Robert et al. 2007).

Sharing information and knowledge about forest conservation is the obligation of the government in this case forest institutions. This is done so that the community has knowledge of the applicable rules related to forest management and preservation. The efforts made by the government must be stronger so that people are motivated

to do positive things with regard to forests that are adjacent to where people live.

B. Build communication

Effective communication according to Susanto (1989) can be seen from the percentage of audiences who can be influenced and those who cannot. In addition the effectiveness of communication can also be known from its effect on audiences namely cognitive affective and conative. Effective communication occurs in a favorable atmosphere using language that is easy to understand and the message arouses the attention and interest of the communicant as a communication partner (Istiyanto 2015). Included in the problem of communication between humans and the environment in which they live. In simple terms the concept is simplified by the term environmental communication.

Building communication reflected by village officials community leaders religious leaders NGOs and youth leaders in establishing communication with the community around the Raja forest has a positive impact on daily life. Building good communication with the community will have an impact on the ease of socialization process of forest conservation. Based on an interview with the former village head who is also the chairman of the forest monitoring community group namely by Mr. Tomas on May 19 2022 that: “We as community leaders have full responsibility for conveying all information related to forest conservation to the community through outreach activities at village halls parties/ceremonies held by the local community and socialization conducted through schools. With this it is very easy for the community to obtain information about how to preserve the forest so that for the community protecting Raja's forest is like guarding their own house”.

This was reinforced by the results of an interview with one of the people who worked as fishermen namely Mr. Harto on May 19 2022 that: “for us the Raja forest is a second home we will fully support whatever information from the government regarding the conservation and management of the Raja forest. We have lived side by side with the king's forest since we were born so whatever we do to the king's forest must comply with the applicable regulations”.

Communication is the best means of conveying or receiving all information both from forest institutions and from the local village government. In the human resource management science family communication is the activity that is most often carried out within the organization namely 75-95% of all organizational activities. of these activities can be broken down 5% for writing 10% for reading 35% speaking and 50% listening. Based on the above it can be concluded that communication is a very important thing that is used in interacting with the community both individually and as a group.

C. Stakeholder Relations

Preserving forests means that we preserve the environment because by saving forests we also save all components of life. If we know something about nature's potential and limiting factors we can determine the best use. New developing ecosystems created by humans such as prairie agriculture irrigated deserts water reservoirs tropical agriculture will last for a long time only if material and energy balances are achieved between the biotic and physical components. Because it is very important to preserve the forest.

Conserving the forest is the same as saving the ecosystem from the forest itself the ecosystem is formed by living and non-living components in a place that interact to form an orderly unit. This order occurs because of the flow of matter and energy which is controlled by the flow of information between the components in the ecosystem. Each component has a function or niche as long as each component performs its function and works well together the orderliness of the ecosystem is maintained. The regularity of the ecosystem shows that the ecosystem is in a certain balance. The balance is not static but dynamic it is always changing sometimes the changes are big and sometimes small. This change can occur naturally or as a human action (Soemarwoto 1983).

From these descriptions we can see that the elements in the environment are not separate but integrated as related components in a system. Naturally saving our forests means saving the environment. Forests that have multiple functions will save all components of life on this earth if we preserve them. The benefits of forest conservation for the environment are numerous globally forests are the lungs of the world and can reduce global warming prevent drought during the dry season and prevent floods and landslides during the rainy season.

Indicators of relations with stakeholders which are reflected in terms of establishing relationships with forest management program stakeholders in the village of Dunu were assessed as good by informants. The influence of the level of community participation in forest management which is caused by good community relations with stakeholders can lead to the successful management of the Raja forest in Dunu village North Gorontalo district. This is in accordance with the results of an interview conducted with Randi as a community member of Dunu village (Interview, 11 June 2022) as follows: “All activities carried out by the community in the context of conserving the Raja forest refer to regulations made by the government in this case forest institutions and this has direct support from community leaders religious leaders and even direct involvement from Rema Muda in Dunu village”.

Another similar thing was conveyed by Mr. Yasin who is a youth leader in Dunu Village (Interview, 12 June 2022) namely: “The government in this case the forest institution always involves us Rema Muda in the socialization process to the village community regarding how to preserve the Dunu forest which is a source of

natural wealth that is invaluable for humans and animals around the forest”.

The indicators for sharing information or knowledge are reflected in the fact that all village officials NGOs community leaders and youth leaders have the opportunity to share information with fellow members of the community to increase knowledge which was considered quite good by the informants. Sharing information or knowledge in the social learning process plays an important role so that it can affect community participation in Raja forest management in Dunu village. Sharing information or knowledge can be done to anyone even to students who go to school around the protected forest area.

This study shows that social learning has a very important role for community participation in the conservation of Raja's forest. The reason is that social learning reflected in building communication between village officials forest institutions and NGOs with the surrounding community has a strong impact on forest conservation. However to further increase community participation it is still necessary to improve the educational background of the community which is still low change the mindset of the people who are too difficult to accept new things especially related to forest conservation and the role of forest institutions that intensively provide socialization to the community about the importance of forests as sustainable forest management Raja of Dunu village.

Based on social learning theory by Albert Bandura that social learning is developed from three assumptions namely; 1) Individuals do learning by imitating what is in their environment especially the behavior of others; 2) Against a strong relationship between students and their environment; 3) The learning outcomes are in the form of visual and verbal behavior codes that are embodied in everyday behavior. Bandura also argued that in the view of learning the function of psychology is explained as a continuous and reciprocal interaction of personal and environmental determinants. Kusumanto et al. (2005) said that the dimensions of social learning are (1) a collection of knowledge development among group members; (2) sharing of knowledge and information among different stakeholders (3) building communication and relationships among stakeholders; and (4) strategic capacity building.

The relationship of social learning to community participation by Berkes (2009) says that social learning is the most efficient step in terms of (1) joint problem solving; (2) reflection on sharing experiences; and (3) share ideas. Social learning is very appropriate when applied to the problem of community participation in development programs. Fernandez et al. (2008) said that the benefits obtained through collaborative resource management can increase understanding and social learning among participants so as to increase trust and a sense of community which has the potential for community resilience. Muro & Jeffry (2012) said that social learning has developed rapidly as a key component of participation and taken specifically as an important element of participation in natural resource management.

Empirical evidence in this study shows that social learning has a very good role in community participation especially in the preservation and management of the Raja forest which is located in the village of Dunu Monano District North Gorontalo Regency. The cause is social learning which is reflected in terms of building communication between forest institutions village government and fellow community groups showing a good role in increasing welfare and the level of community participation.

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